

THE QUALITY OF DRINKING WATER AND WASTEWATER, THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON PUBLIC LIFE AND HUMAN HEALTH

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7734094>

ELSEVIER

International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities

Khayriniso Jurayeva

Student of the department of International Journalism
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: In this article, the causes, consequences and solutions of climate warming, people's health in the face of climate change, disputes about solar warming, the damage of ice melting to nature, how to protect people from heat, drinking water and much more. this article discusses other points related to warm days, comments are taken into account.

Keywords: climate warming, drought, man of the year, drinking water, discussion, causes of climate warming.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 12-03-2023

Accepted: 13-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a dangerous factor for nature, the atmosphere and humans in the current era of industrial development. In each country, a large number of enterprises are put into operation, and various gases or substances are emitted into the air. This has led to a change in the atmosphere now.

Since their inception, these businesses have contributed to climate change, reduced rainfall and global warming. For example, scientists say that since 1975 the average air temperature has risen by 0.15-0.20 °C every 10 years. If the temperature rises again in the future, then within a year the temperature could rise to +4 degrees.

Most of Africa's population is dying from heat and hunger. When the air temperature rises, moisture in the soil is lost, which can lead to a poor harvest. It can also be said that the heat in the regions causes the excitation of various substances in the human body and makes a person sick.

According to some forecasts, since the turn of the century, the death rate from heat conditions among the elderly worldwide has increased by 54%, reaching 296,000 in 2018. "About 400 million people are expected to be unable to work outside due to heat waves," said Daniel Quiggin, a scientist at Chatham House, which produced the report. Heat waves and droughts also affect food security. The loss of crops and the growth of pests and diseases cause prices to rise. East Africa was the victim of a locust invasion last year. [1]

ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY OF THE LITERATURE

In 1958, Charles David Keeling completed his scientific work measuring CO² and found that the substance had doubled during the current period of industrialization. Thus, it can be said that the reduction of industrial plants, greenhouses and oil extraction plants will benefit the atmosphere. As a result of air warming, the amount of melting ice in the Arctic Ocean has increased by a very large percentage, and the rise in water levels, according to scientists, has increased by 7.7 cm.

Jason Mark Gregar, a resident of Prince Edward Island, Canada, said he would not start a family because of the environmental benefits, and also noted that this island has a lot of typhoons due to rising water levels every year. To take a simple example, as a result of climate warming, many forests have burned to the ground, many rare animal species have disappeared, floods have washed away settlements in areas due to rising water levels, and, most importantly, climate change does not affect people's health.

In rural areas, located near industrial enterprises, a large number of disabled children are born: hairless, without fingers, premature. That is why old people die early, and young people become sick and toothless. The salt accumulated as a result of the drying up of the Aral Sea caused damage to the local population. These include an increase in the number of mentally and physically handicapped people and the aging of the elderly.

Global warming will cause changes in the distribution of atmospheric deposits. This creates a shortage of fresh water supplies, especially clean drinking water. As a result, the population is at increased risk of poor hygiene and diarrheal disease. At the same time, 760,000 children under the age of 5 worldwide die every year from diarrheal diseases, and global warming is exacerbating the problem. In addition, lack of water leads to famine and drought. By the end of this century, climate change could lead to further increases in regional and global droughts. Also during a heat wave, the level of pollination of plants and other aeroallergens increases, and they cause asthma, which affects more than 300 million people on earth. [2]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In December 2019, The Time's magazine named Greta Tumberg Person of the Year. He urged many people to call for climate change and said, "I want you to take this issue seriously." His words became the "Word of the Year". This demonstration was attended by many people in the regions. The best way to prevent climate warming is to increase the number of forests. Over the past 10 years, forests have been severely cut down in places.

7 years ago, US President Barack Obama held a scientific meeting about the sudden rise in temperature. In his speech, he mentions the reproduction of forests,

obtaining full electrical energy from the sun and wind. He also noted that reducing greenhouses is also good for nature.

At a virtual press conference earlier this week in Geneva, Claire Nullis, spokesperson for the UN World Meteorological Organization (WMO), said that measurements made since the beginning of the year suggest temperatures in the northern hemisphere may rise to a record high in 2020. He stressed that the coronavirus epidemic makes it difficult to take preventive measures in this regard, and said that it is necessary to protect communities and people. He warned to be prepared for extremely high temperatures. [3]

What are the recommendations for thermal protection?

The following recommendations were made in a package of measures shared through the WMO social media pages:

- going out into the street in a hat with an umbrella to protect from the heat;
- drink enough water;
- wash your wrists with cold water;
- massage with alcohol to speed up blood circulation in the legs;
- applying ice compresses to the forehead and shoulders;
- Turn off electrical appliances and artificial lights or any other heat sources.

[4]

CONCLUSION

People need clean air to live and breathe. Although in the modern world we cannot suddenly abandon cars and burning fossils, nevertheless, on our planet, all supporters of environmental cleanliness, the purity of nature, and the conservation of natural resources. Therefore, International Climate Day is a holiday not only for environmental safety specialists, climatologists, environmental organizations and scientists, but for all mankind. [5]

I would say that if we all do not take our part in the fight against climate change now, this indicator will worsen year by year. Frequent droughts and rising temperatures in places can harm people's lifestyles and health. Planting more trees in the regions is not without benefits. If we all worked together, we could prevent climate change. Let's not ignore this situation.

REFERENCES:

1. www.amerikaovozi.com (<http://www.amerikaovozi.com/>) “ Iqlim o'zgarishining insoniyatga ta'siri qanday? ”.
2. Iroda Toshmatova “ Tabiatning qon bosimi oshmoqda ” www.marifat.uz (<http://www.marifat.uz/>)

3. www.kun.uz (<http://www.kun.uz/>) “ Havo nega isib ketmoqda: insoniyatga qanday xavf bor? ”.
4. www.kun.uz (<http://www.kun.uz/>) “ Havo nega isib ketmoqda: insoniyatga qanday xavf bor? ”.
5. Iroda Toshmatova “ Tabiatning qon bosimi oshmoqda ” www.marifat.uz (<http://www.marifat.uz/>)